

Preparation of Some *o*- and *m*-Halophenyl Derivatives of Tin

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o-(fluoro) and *o*- and *m*- (chloro, bromo and iodo) phenyl triphenyl/ethyl/*n*-propyl/*n*-butyl tin derivatives have been prepared for the first time by *in situ* formation and reaction of grignard reagents from ortho and meta iodo halo benzenes respectively with tri-phenyl/ethyl/*n*-propyl/*n*-butyl tin chloride. Some *o*- and *m*- Bis(trialkyl tin) benzenes have also been prepared.

In continuation of the earlier work¹⁻³, the preparation of some *o*- and *m*- halophenyl derivatives of tin has been attempted by the improved method.

EXPERIMENTAL

o- and *m*- iodo-halobenzenes and di-iodobenzenes were prepared from *o*- and *m*- nitro-aniline as the starting materials and purified in the laboratory by well known methods.

Tetra phenyl tin was prepared by the reaction of stannic chloride with chlorobenzene in benzene containing sodium metal wire⁴. By reacting tetraphenyl tin and stannic chloride in requisite quantities, triphenyl tin chloride was prepared and purified⁵. Triethyl tin chloride⁶, tri-*n*-propyl tin chloride⁶ and tri-*n*-butyl tin chloride⁷ were prepared by the methods reported in the literature.

The required iodo-halo benzene dissolved in suitable quantity of dry diethyl ether was added to a mixture of triphenyl/triethyl/tri-*n*-propyl/tri-*n*-butyl tin chloride and magnesium metal of grignard specifications, taken in calculated quantities in dry diethyl ether as solvent, in a three necked pyrex flask equipped with a dropping funnel on one side, double walled water condenser on the other side and a mechanical stirrer through the central neck. Continuous stirring and refluxing were maintained till the reaction ceased and whole of magnesium was consumed. Unreacted grignard reagent, if any, was hydrolysed, the ethereal layer separated and the end product collected.

Similarly *o*-Bis (triethyl tin) benzene and *m*-Bis (triethyl/tri *n*-propyl/tri *n*-butyl tin) benzenes were prepared by using the reactants in calculated quantities.

Absence of other isomers in all the compounds was shown by vapour phase chromatography.

All these compounds with relative information are recorded in table I.

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TABLE I

o- and *m*-halophenyl derivatives of tin

Magnesium taken = 0.5 g (1.0 g in the case of Bis-derivatives).

S.No.	Dihalobenzene used (g)	Refluxing time (hr.)	Product	Liquid/Solid (l/s)	m.pt./b.pt. (°C)	Yield %	Sn %	
							Found	Calcd.
(a) Reaction with triphenyl tin chloride (8.02 g.)								
1.	<i>o</i> -iodo fluorobenzene (3.53)	10	<i>o</i> fluorophenyl triphenyl tin	(s)	m.pt. 180-182	53.00	26.5	26.74
2.	<i>o</i> -iodo chlorobenzene (3.98)	18	<i>o</i> -chlorophenyl triphenyl tin.	(s)	m.pt. 191-194	64.00	25.70	25.74
3.	<i>o</i> -iodo bromobenzene (4.75)	24	<i>o</i> -bromophenyl triphenyl tin	(s)	m.pt. 218-221	54.00	23.37	23.50
4.	<i>o</i> -diiodobenzene (5.53)	20	<i>o</i> -iodophenyl triphenyl	(s)	m.pt. 205-208	45.50	21.56	21.52
5.	<i>m</i> -iodochlorobenzene (3.99)	20	<i>m</i> -chlorophenyl triphenyl tin	(s)	m.pt. 135-136	50.00	25.76	25.74
6.	<i>m</i> -iodobromobenzene (4.74)	21	<i>m</i> -bromophenyl triphenyl tin	(s)	m.pt. 180-181	55.30	23.25	28.50
7.	<i>m</i> diiodobenzene (5.52)	23	<i>m</i> -iodophenyl triphenyl tin.	(s)	m.pt. 185-188	52.10	20.42	21.52
(b) Reaction with triethyl tin chloride (5.03 g 10.1 g in case of bis-derivatives)								
8.	<i>o</i> -iodofluorobenzene (3.68)	14	<i>o</i> -fluorophenyl triethyl tin.	(l)	b.pt. 140-142/4 mm	56.50	38.50	39.50
9.	<i>o</i> -iodochlorobenzene (3.97)	12	<i>o</i> -chlorophenyl triethyl tin.	(l)	b.pt. 135-137/4 mm	58.00	36.80	37.40
10.	<i>o</i> -iodobromobenzene (4.72)	16	<i>o</i> -bromophenyl triethyl tin.	(l)	b.pt. 150-155/4 mm	55.00	31.80	32.80
11.	<i>o</i> -diiodobenzene (5.50)	16	<i>o</i> -iodophenyl triethyl tin.	(l)	b.pt. 162-165/4 mm	52.00	28.90	29.02
12.	<i>o</i> -diiodobenzene (5.50)	18	<i>o</i> -Bis(triethyl tin) benzene.	(l)	b.pt. 100-106/4 mm	49.00	48.30	48.70
13.	<i>m</i> -iodochlorobenzene (3.59)	16	<i>m</i> -chlorophenyl triethyl tin.	(l)	b.pt 115-117/3 mm	51.00	36.62	37.40
14.	<i>m</i> -iodobromobenzene (4.80)	16	<i>m</i> -bromophenyl triethyl tin.	(l)	b.pt. 125-127/3 mm	60.00	32.00	32.80
15.	<i>m</i> -diiodobenzene (5.65)	25	<i>m</i> -iodophenyl triethyl tin.	(l)	b.pt. 155-160/4 mm	50.00	28.38	29.02
16.	<i>m</i> -diiodobenzene (5.66)	26	<i>m</i> -Bis(triethyl tin) benzene.	(l)	b.pt. 130-135/4 mm	46.00	47.80	48.70

TABLE I—Contd.

S.N	Dihalobenzene used (g)	Refluxing time (hr.)	Product	Liquid/Solid (l/s)	m.pt./b.pt. (°C)	Yield %	Sn %	
							Found	Calcd.
(c) Reaction with tri- <i>n</i> -propyl tin chloride (5.90 g 11.80 g in case of bis-derivatives)								
17.	<i>m</i> -iodochlorobenzene (4.11)	15	<i>m</i> -chlorophenyl tin <i>n</i> -propyl tin.	(l)	b.pt. 175–180/6 mm	50.00	32.77	33.10
18.	<i>m</i> -iodobromobenzene (4.76)	16	<i>m</i> -bromophenyl tri <i>n</i> -propyl tin	(l)	b.pt. 178–180/6 mm	49.20	29.07	29.45
19.	<i>m</i> -diiodobenzene (5.50)	20	<i>m</i> -iodophenyl tin <i>n</i> -propyl tin.	(l)	b.pt. 124–125/6 mm	52.70	26.20	26.38
20.	<i>m</i> -iodobromobenzene (4.83)	20	<i>m</i> -Bis(tri <i>n</i> -propyl tin) benzene.	(l)	b.pt. 202–204/6 mm	32.40	40.72	41.60
(d) Reaction with tri <i>n</i> -butyl tin chloride (6.68 g 13.36 g in case of bis-derivatives)								
21.	<i>m</i> -iodochlorobenzene (4.07)	16	<i>m</i> -chlorophenyl tri <i>n</i> -butyl tin.	(l)	b.pt. 140–150/4 mm	60.00	28.61	29.68
22.	<i>m</i> -iodobromobenzene (4.74)	16	<i>m</i> -bromophenyl tri <i>n</i> -butyl tin.	(l)	b.pt. 155–160/4 mm	62.00	27.25	26.51
23.	<i>m</i> diiodobenzene (5.50)	25	<i>m</i> -iodophenyl tri <i>n</i> -butyl tin.	(l)	b.pt. 155–160/3 mm	53.00	23.20	23.98
24.	<i>m</i> -iodobromobenzene (4.88)	16	<i>m</i> -Bis(tri <i>n</i> -butyl tin) benzene.	(l)	b.pt. 143/4 mm	47.00	36.20	36.09

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